

FILES AND FOLDERS ORGANIZATION

FOLDER TYPE:

- Exp_results: Matlab structure containing the experimental results against which the mechanical model is validated. They are obtained from the data paper: *Tarquini et al. 2019*, Uniaxial Cyclic Tests on Reinforced Concrete Members with Lap Splices, Earthquake Spectra and organized in a unique matlab structure.
- Figure_x...: Each folder contains the required files to plot one or more figures from the paper: 'Extended tension chord model for boundary elements of RC walls accounting for anchorage slip and lap splices presence'.

FILE TYPE:

- MAIN...: The file to run. It contains all the inputs, call all the required subroutines and produces the main figures
- COMPUTE...: Files performing different types of calculations. Specific descriptions are provided in the files
- DISCRETIZATION...: In this routine file it is performed the discretization of the TU in the required tension chord units
- Load_exp: subroutine loading the experimental files
- TUtoProperties: subroutine returning the main parameters of a TU given the TU number
- Plot...: Files creating variables required for the main plots and plotting different types of features
- LAP_P/C...: files performing a specific task on a specific unit